

1 **Supplemental material**

2 For the manuscript “Simulation of coronary fractional flow reserve and whole-cycle flow based on optical
3 coherence tomography in individual patients with coronary artery disease” by Niels Thue Olsen, MD, PhD
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16 Model description

17 Detailed description of the simulation model. See Figure 1 in main article for a diagram of the model.

18 *Region of interest (ROI)*

19 The stenotic part of the epicardial coronary artery measured with OCT, the region of interest (ROI), is
20 modeled as a series of short tube segments with a measured lumen area [and a maximal and minimal
21 diameter]. For the simulation, the observed area is corrected with the following formula:

$$22 \quad A_{lumen,sim}(x) = A_{lumen,obs}(x) + k_{wirecorr} + k_{lumencorr} \cdot 2\pi \cdot \sqrt{A_{lumen,obs}(x)/\pi}$$

23 where $A_{lumen,sim}(x)$ is the corrected lumen area used for the simulation at position x along the ROI in the
24 direction from proximal to distal, $A_{lumen,obs}(x)$ is the observed lumen area from OCT, $k_{wirecorr}$ is a correction
25 factor to account for the cross-sectional area of the coronary pressure wire during measurements (set to -
26 0.1 mm^2), and $k_{lumencorr}$ is an empirical correction factor of the lumen radius.

27 A proximal ($A_{lumen,proximalref}$) and a distal reference lumen area ($A_{lumen,distalref}$) is manually selected based on the
28 most healthy segments of the coronary artery, and a reference area, $A_{lumen,ref}(x)$, is defined for the entire
29 length of the ROI, based on a linear decrease in reference area from the proximal to the distal end.

30 *Side-branch flow*

31 The reduction in flow through the ROI due to side-branch flow is modeled to be related to the decrease in
32 reference lumen area compared to proximal reference lumen area in accordance with the Huo-Kassab
33 scaling law (1), so that

$$34 \quad Q_{rel}(x) = \left(\frac{A_{lumen,ref}(x)}{A_{lumen,proximalref}} \right)^{7/6}$$

35 where $Q_{rel}(x)$ is the ratio of coronary flow at the present position of the ROI to coronary flow at the ROI
 36 inlet.

37 *ROI resistance and flow*

38 The resistance to flow is modeled to be composed of two components: 1) A viscous resistance proportional
 39 to flow, and 2) a non-linear component caused by flow convergence, proportional to quadratic flow. The
 40 model assumes no pressure recovery in the flow divergence zone.

41 The relation between flow and pressure difference along the ROI is expressed as

$$42 \quad \Delta P = K_{visc} \cdot Q + K_{conv} \cdot Q^2$$

43 where Q is the coronary flow at the ROI inlet, and ΔP is the pressure difference between the proximal end
 44 (assumed equal to aortic pressure) and the distal end of the ROI.

45 K_{visc} , a coefficient representing viscous resistance of the entire ROI corrected for side-branch flow, is
 46 calculated according to the Hagen-Poiseuille equation as

$$47 \quad K_{visc} = \sum_{x=0}^{ROI \text{ length}} \left(\frac{8\pi\mu}{A_{lumen,sim}(x)^2} \right) \cdot Q_{rel} \cdot \Delta x$$

48 where μ is dynamic viscosity of blood (set to 4 mPa·s).

49 K_{conv} , the coefficient representing flow convergence losses for the entire ROI, is calculated as

$$50 \quad K_{conv} = \sum_{x=0}^{ROI \text{ length}} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{Q_{rel}(x)^2}{A_{lumen,sim}(x)^2} - \frac{Q_{rel}(x - \Delta x)^2}{A_{lumen,sim}(x - \Delta x)^2} \right) \cdot \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot K_t, & acc > 0 \\ 0, & acc \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

51 where acc is the difference between the relative change in $A_{lumen,sim}$ and the relative change in $A_{lumen,ref}$
 52 (where this is positive, flow accelerates along the ROI). ρ is the density of blood ($1.06 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$). K_t is an
 53 empirical constant traditionally added to the equation, here set to 1.

54 The flow equation can be rearranged as

$$55 \quad K_{conv} \cdot Q^2 + K_{visc} \cdot Q - \Delta P = 0$$

56 When only forward flow is considered, Q can thus be calculated as the positive root of a second-degree
57 polynomial:

$$58 \quad Q = \begin{cases} \left(K_{visc} - \sqrt{K_{visc}^2 + 4 \cdot K_{conv} \cdot \Delta P} \right) / (-2 \cdot K_{conv}), & \Delta P > 0 \\ 0, & \Delta P \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

59 Flow at the distal end of the ROI into the distal epicardial vasculature is calculated as

$$60 \quad Q_{dist} = Q \cdot \left(\frac{A_{lumen,distalref}}{A_{lumen,proximalref}} \right)^{7/6}$$

61 The distal epicardial arteries are modeled as a windkessel component with constant, linear compliance and
62 time-varying pressure and volume: $P_{dist}(t) = C_{dist} \cdot V_{dist}(t)$, where P_{dist} is pressure, C_{dist} is compliance and V_{dist} is
63 volume. C_{dist} is scaled to the reference size of the distal part of the epicardial artery: $C_{dist} = A_{lumen,distalref} \cdot 0.2$
64 $\mu\text{L} \cdot \text{mmHg}^{-1} \cdot \text{mm}^{-2}$.

65 The microvasculature is modeled in the same way: $P_{micro}(t) = C_{micro} \cdot V_{micro}(t)$, where P_{micro} is pressure, C_{micro} is
66 compliance and V_{micro} is volume. C_{micro} is calculated based on the distal reference area of the ROI: $C_{micro} =$
67 $A_{lumen,distalref} \cdot 0.8 \mu\text{L} \cdot \text{mmHg}^{-1} \cdot \text{mm}^{-2}$.

68 Microvascular resistance distal to the ROI is calculated based on an empirical relationship between artery
69 reference size and microvascular conductance:

$$70 \quad R_{micro} = \frac{1}{G_{10} \cdot (A_{lumen,distalref} / 10 \text{ mm}^2)^{7/6}}$$

71 where G_{10} is the empirical microvascular conductance (1/resistance) at a reference vessel area of 10 mm^2 .

72 Microvascular resistance is divided into two components in series, a proximal component $R_{micro,prox}$ (75% of
73 R_{micro}) and a distal component $R_{micro,dist}$ (25% of R_{micro}) (2).

74 Flow from the distal epicardial vasculature into the microvasculature is calculated as

$$75 \quad Q_{micro,in} = (P_{dist} - P_{micro})/R_{micro,prox}$$

76 and flow out of the microvasculature into the coronary venous compartment is calculated as

$$77 \quad Q_{micro,out} = (P_{micro} - P_{ven,eff})/R_{micro,dist}$$

78 where $P_{ven,eff}$ is effective coronary venous pressure.

79 *Effective venous pressure and myocardial-vessel interaction*

80 To account for the effect of myocardial contraction and the change in LV cavity pressure on coronary flow,
81 effective coronary venous pressure with respect to intramyocardial pressure is calculated as the highest
82 value of either the instantaneous average intramyocardial pressure or the right atrial pressure:

$$83 \quad P_{ven,eff} = \begin{cases} P_{LV} \cdot LVPratio, & P_{LV} \cdot LVPratio > P_{RA} \\ P_{RA}, & P_{LV} \cdot LVPratio \leq P_{RA} \end{cases}$$

84 The average instantaneous intramyocardial pressure is calculated as a constant fraction ($LVPratio$) of LV
85 cavity pressure, for all calculations this constant was set at 0.5 assuming an even distribution of
86 microvascular vessels and a linear decline in intramyocardial pressure through the LV wall from the
87 endocardial to the epicardial surface (3). P_{RA} was set to 2 mmHg.

88

89 References

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97

98

99

101 Supplemental Table S1. Patient characteristics

Characteristic	n = 41
Age	65.4 (8.7)
Male, n (%)	28 (68%)
Height, cm (SD)	175 (9)
Weight, kg (SD)	88 (15)
BMI, kg/m ² (SD)	28.6 (4.0)
Smoking, current or previous, n (%)	27 (66%)
Hypertension, n (%)	26 (63%)
Dyslipidemia, n (%)	30 (73%)
Diabetes, n (%)	5 (12%)
COPD, n (%)	4 (9.8%)
Atrial fibrillation*, n (%)	3 (7.3%)
Chronic kidney disease, n (%)	0 (0%)
Peripheral arterial disease, n (%)	2 (4.9%)
Previous MI, n (%)	4 (9.8%)
Previous PCI, n (%)	8 (20%)
Previous CABG, n (%)	1 (2.4%)
CCS class ≥ 2, n (%)	30 (73%)
NYHA class ≥ 2, n (%)	16 (39%)
Systolic BP, mmHg (SD)	143 (20)
Diastolic BP, mmHg (SD)	81 (11)
HR, min ⁻¹ (SD)	68 (12)
LVEF, % (SD)	56.5 (6.4)
Creatinine, μmol/L (SD)	73 (13)
Medications	

Aspirin, n (%)	33 (80%)
P2Y12-blocker, n (%)	6 (15%)
OAC, n (%)	3 (7.3%)
Statin, n (%)	39 (95%)
Beta blocker, n (%)	19 (46%)
Long-acting nitrate, n (%)	10 (24%)
Calcium antagonist, n (%)	12 (29%)
ACE inhibitor, n (%)	10 (24%)
ARB, n (%)	9 (22%)
Oral antidiabetic, n (%)	4 (9.8%)
Insulin, n (%)	2 (4.9%)

102 BMI: Body mass index, COPD: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, MI: Myocardial infarction, PCI:
103 Percutaneous coronary intervention, CABG: Coronary artery bypass grafting, CCS: Canadian Cardiovascular
104 Society, NYHA: New York Heart Association, BP: Blood pressure, HR: Heart rate, LVEF: Left ventricular
105 ejection fraction, OAC: Oral anticoagulant, ARB: Angiotensin II receptor blocker

106 * Atrial fibrillation was paroxysmal in all cases and not present at time of examination

107

Supplemental Table S2. Detailed lesion characteristics

Lesion Characteristics	n = 48
Coronary artery, n	
LAD	28 (58%)
Cx	13 (27%)
RCA	7 (15%)
Angiographic diameter stenosis, %	53 (14)
Intracoronary physiology	
Pa(rest), mmHg	88 (12)
Pd(rest), mmHg	81 (13)
Pd/Pa(rest)	0.93 (0.08)
RFR	0.90 (0.13)
Pa(hyperemia), mmHg	83 (14)
Pd(hyperemia), mmHg	66 (16)
FFR	0.79 (0.14)
CFR *	4.35 (3.21)
IMR, mmHg·s *	20 (10)
Q(hyperemia), mL/s *	2.58 (1.51) **
R(hyperemia), mmHg/(mL/s) *	36.9 (35.4) **
Optical coherence tomography	
Reference vessel area, mm ²	10.8 (4.5)
Minimal lumen area, mm ²	2.62 (1.61)
Area stenosis, %	49 (28)
Diameter stenosis, %	65 (26)
Plaque burden, %	76 (11)

109

Continuous measures reported as mean (SD), categorical as n (%). * In 1 lesion, CFR, IMR, Q and R was not

110

available, so n = 47 for these. ** In units as reported by the Coroventis software, Q(hyperemia) was 0.155 ±

111

0.090 L/min, R(hyperemia) was 614 ± 590 mmHg/(L/min).

112

113 **Supplemental Table S3. Model parameters with sensitivity analysis**

Model Parameter	Value	Relative Sensitivity of Model Output (FFR)
Input stenosis parameters		
Proximal reference lumen area	10 mm ²	-0.205
Distal reference lumen area	5 mm ²	-0.169
K _{visc}	2.68 mmHg·s·mL ⁻¹	-
K _{conv}	2.81 mmHg·s ² ·mL ⁻²	-
Fixed parameters		
Blood density	1060 kg/m ³	-0.134
Blood viscosity	4 mPa·s	-0.052
k _{wirecorr}	-0.1 mm ²	-0.029
k _{lumencorr}	-0.075 mm	-0.100
K _t	1	-0.134
Scaling factor for distal epicardial artery compliance	0.2 μL·mmHg ⁻¹ ·mm ⁻²	0.002
Scaling factor for distal microvascular compliance	0.8 μL·mmHg ⁻¹ ·mm ⁻²	-0.0003
G ₁₀ (LAD)	0.064 mL·mmHg ⁻¹ ·s ⁻¹	-0.321
Ratio of proximal to distal microvascular resistance	0.75	0.001
LV cavity pressure microvascular compression ratio	0.5	0.184
Bifurcation factor	7/6	0.139
RA pressure	2 mmHg	0.002

114 For sensitivity analysis, simulations were run with the input parameters of an individual lesion with
 115 intermediate severity (FFR = 0.79). The sensitivity of simulated FFR was now tested for the relevant
 116 parameters by increasing each parameter value at a time by 1%. The proportional change in FFR divided by
 117 the proportional change in parameter value is reported as relative sensitivity.

118 The model output evaluated as simulated FFR was moderately sensitive to the manually entered input
119 parameters of reference vessel size proximally and distally, to empirical constant K_t , to empirical lumen
120 correction constant $k_{\text{lumencorr}}$, and to LV cavity pressure microvascular compression ratio (relative
121 sensitivities between 0.10 and 0.21). The model output was highly sensitive to the conductance ratio G_{10}
122 relating microvascular resistance to reference vessel size (relative sensitivity 0.32).

123

125 **Supplemental Figure S1. Calibration of simulated average coronary flow with observed values.**

126

127 Agreement is shown after calibrating reference conductance separately for LAD and for Cx/RCA. Data for 47

128 lesions are shown (in one LAD-lesion, absolute flow measurement was not available). Whisker plots are

129 mean difference \pm 1 SD.

130

131 Coronary model JSim code

```

132 import nsrunit;
133     unit conversion on;
134     unit mN = 0.001 N;
135     unit Pa = 1 N/m^2;
136     unit mPa = 0.001 Pa;
137     unit kPa = 1000 Pa;
138     unit mm = 0.001 m;
139     unit min = 60000 ms;
140
141     math coronary_model{
142
143     realDomain    t    ms;
144     t.min=0; t.max=100000; t.delta=10;
145
146     realDomain    x    mm;
147     x.min=0; x.max=75; x.delta=0.2;
148
149     real          // PARAMETERS
150 // GLOBAL PARAMETERS
151
152     rho          = 1060 kg/m^3,    // Density of blood
153     visc         = 4 mPa*s, // Dynamic viscosity of blood
154
155     x_oct        = 0.2 mm, // OCT distance btw points
156
157     AreaCorrection= -0.1 mm^2,      // Correction of measured area - to correct for wire e.g.
158
159     LumenCorrection = -0.075 mm,    // Correction of measured lumen radius - to correct for modality-
160 specific differences and obtain effective lumen area
161
162 // Manual settings for prox. and dist ref. areas
163
164
165     ProxRefArea   = 8 mm^2,          // Proximal lumen reference (for manual input)
166     DistRefArea   = 4 mm^2,          // Distal lumen reference (for manual input)
167
168 // Compliances
169     C_dist_ratio  = 0.0002 mL*mmHg^(-1)*mm^(-2), // Compliance of distal coronary arteries per mm2
170 reference area
171     C_micro_ratio = 0.0008 mL*mmHg^(-1)*mm^(-2), // Compliance of distal intramyocardial
172 microvasculature per mm2 reference area
173
174     C_dist        = C_dist_ratio*DistRefArea, // Corrected for ref size of distal artery
175     C_micro       = C_micro_ratio*DistRefArea, // Corrected for ref size of distal artery
176
177 // Unstressed volumes
178     V0_dist      = 0 mL,             // Unstressed volume of distal coronary arteries
179     V0_micro     = 0 mL,             // Unstressed volume of microvasculature
180
181 // Empirical coefficients
182     Kt           = 1 dimensionless, // Empirical coefficient for pressure loss due to flow convergence (Adapted
183 from Young et al. 1977)
184
185     BifurcFactor = 1.1667 dimensionless, // Exponential factor to area to obtain proportionality with flow
186 (for Huo-Kassab = 7/6)

```

```

187
188 // Resistances
189     Conduct10    = 0.064 1/(mmHg*s*mL^(-1)),           // Empirical microvascular conductance (1/R) at
190 an epicardial reference area of 10 mm2
191     R_micrototal = 1/(Conduct10*(ProxRefArea/(10 mm^2))^BifurcFactor), // Microvascular resistance
192 (arterioles, capillaries, venules) for entire vascular bed distal of proximal ROI
193     R_micro      = R_micrototal/((DistRefArea/ProxRefArea)^BifurcFactor), // Microvascular resistance
194 (arterioles, capillaries, venules) from vascular bed distal to distal ROI
195     RatioProxMVR = 0.75,                               // Ratio of arteriole + 1/2 capillary resistance compared to venular + 1/2
196 capillary (Munneke 2022)
197     R_microprox  = R_micro*RatioProxMVR,               // The resistance modeled to be proximal to the
198 microvascular capacitor
199     R_microdist  = R_micro*(1-RatioProxMVR), // - distal to the capacitor.
200
201 // Parameters for estimation of LV pressure effect on microvasculature
202     RatioLVp    = 0.5 dimensionless,                 // Ratio for transmission of LV cavity pressure to microcirc
203
204 // Timer settings
205     BPwindow    = 3000 ms;                          // Window for measuring BP
206
207 //
208 private real
209
210     HRconverter = 60000 ms/min;
211
212 // Initial conditions
213
214
215
216
217 // -----
218 // VARIABLES
219 // -----
220
221 // VARIABLES
222
223
224 extern real
225 // Pressure input
226     P_ao(t)    mmHg,           // Measured aortic curve
227     P_lv(t)    mmHg,           // Measured LV pressure
228     P_ra      mmHg,           // Right atrial pressure
229
230 // Morphology input
231     Areaobs(x) mm^2,           // Measured area
232     MaxDobs(x) mm,             // Measured max diameter
233     MinDobs(x) mm;            // Measured min diameter
234
235 real
236
237 // Morphology
238     AreaCor(x) mm^2,           // Effective coronary area
239     AreaChange(x) mm^2,       // Area change
240
241     AreaRef(x) mm^2,           // Reference area at point x
242
243     Q_rel(x)   dimensionless, // Flow at x compared to flow at entry after correcting for sidebranch loss
244

```

```

245 // Pressures
246
247     P_dist(t)  mmHg,      // Pressure of distal epicardial arteries
248     P_micro(t) mmHg,      // Pressure of microvasculature ("mid")
249     P_ven(t)   mmHg,      // Coronary venous pressure
250     P_roi(t,x) mmHg,      // Instantaneous pressure along the ROI
251
252
253 // Flows
254     Q_roi(t)mL*s^(-1),    // Coronary flow into proximal ROI
255     Q_roidist(t) mL*s^(-1), // Coronary flow from ROI to distal arteries
256     Q_mvin(t)  mL*s^(-1), // Coronary flow from distal epi arteries into microvasculature
257     Q_mvout(t) mL*s^(-1), // Coronary flow from microvasculature into coronary veins
258
259 // Volumes
260     V_dist(t)  mL,        // Volume of distal epicardial arteries
261     V_micro(t) mL,        // Volume of microvasculature
262
263 // Resistance coefficients
264     R_roi(x)   mmHg*s*mL^(-1),
265     R_roisum   mmHg*s*mL^(-1),
266     R2_roi(x)  mmHg*s^2*mL^(-2),
267     R2_roisum mmHg*s^2*mL^(-2);
268
269
270 // -----
271 // INITIAL CONDITIONS
272 // -----
273
274 // Initial Conditions
275
276     when(t=t.min) {
277 // Volumes
278         V_dist = 0;
279         V_micro = 0;
280     }
281
282
283
284 // -----
285 // SYSTEM OF EQUATIONS
286 // -----
287
288
289
290 // Area equations
291
292     AreaCor      = Areaobs+AreaCorrection+LumenCorrection*PI*2*(Areaobs/PI)^.5; // if correction for
293 hydraulic area add: "** 2 * MaxDobs * MinDobs / (MaxDobs^2+MinDobs^2)"
294     AreaChange   = AreaCor(x) - AreaCor(x-x.delta);
295
296     AreaRef      = ProxRefArea - (ProxRefArea-DistRefArea)/(x.max-x.min)*x;
297
298     Q_rel        = (AreaRef/ProxRefArea)^(BifurcFactor);
299
300 // ROI Coronary resistance and flow
301
302     // Viscous resistance to be multiplied by flow

```

```

303 R_roi      = 8*PI*visc/(AreaCor^2)*x.delta      // Viscous resistance
304          * Q_rel ;                          // Corrected for lower flow more distally due to sidebranch flow
305 R_roi sum  = sum(R_roi@x);                    // Summary coefficient for entire ROI
306
307          // Flow convergence non-linear effect to be multiplied by squared flow
308          // (assuming no pressure recovery)
309 R2_roi     = if (AreaCor(x)/AreaCor(x-x.delta)<Q_rel(x)/Q_rel(x-x.delta)) // Flow is only
310 accelerated if area decreases more than reference area
311          (Q_rel(x)^2/AreaCor(x)^2-Q_rel(x-x.delta)^2/AreaCor(x-x.delta)^2)*rho/2 // Pressure loss
312 due to convergent acceleration, corrected for lower flow more distally due to sidebranch flow assuming area
313 conservation
314          * Kt                                // Empirical coefficient
315          //
316          else
317          0 ;
318 R2_roi sum  = sum(R2_roi@x);                    // Summary coefficient for entire ROI
319
320          // Flow is calculated based on pressure difference and the linear and quadratic components
321          // Only antegrade flow is allowed
322          // Solved as positive root of a second degree polynomial
323          // R2*Q^2 + R*Q - dP = 0
324
325 Q_roi      = if((P_ao-P_dist) > 0)
326          (R_roi sum - sqrt(R_roi sum^2+4*R2_roi sum*(P_ao-P_dist)))/(-2*R2_roi sum)
327          else
328          0 ;
329
330 Q_roidist  = Q_roi*(DistRefArea/ProxRefArea)^(BifurcFactor);
331
332 P_roi      = P_ao - sum(x = x.min to x, R_roi)*Q_roi - sum(x = x.min to x, R2_roi)*Q_roi^2; // Local
333 pressure along the ROI (monitor)
334
335          // Effective distal venule pressure
336
337 P_ven      = if (P_lv*RatioLVp > P_ra)
338          P_lv*RatioLVp
339          else
340          P_ra;
341
342          // Coronary flow
343
344 Q_mvin     = if ((P_dist-P_micro<0) and (V_micro<=0))
345          0
346          else
347          (P_dist-P_micro)/R_microprox;
348 Q_mvout    = if ((P_micro-P_ven>0) and (V_micro<=0))
349          0
350          else
351          (P_micro-P_ven)/R_microdist;
352
353          // Conservation of mass equations
354
355 V_dist:t=  Q_roidist-Q_mvin;
356 V_micro:t  = Q_mvin-Q_mvout;
357
358          // Vessel pressures
359
360 P_dist     = (V_dist-V0_dist)/C_dist;

```

```
361      P_micro      = (V_micro-V0_micro)/C_micro + P_lv*RatioLVp;
362
363
364 } // END OF MML CODE
365
366 /*
367
368 Original author: Niels Thue Olsen 2023.
369
370 Developed for the JSim software platform:
371 Copyright (C) 1999-2009 University of Washington. From the National Simulation Resource,
372 Director J. B. Bassingthwaighe, Department of Bioengineering, University of Washington, Seattle WA
373 98195-5061.
374 Academic use is unrestricted. Software may be copied so long as this copyright notice is included.
375
376 */
377
```